

Evaluation of Prognostic Factors in Outcome of Bowel Anastomosis: A Hospital Based Study

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Abstract:

Background: Bowel anastomosis is the surgical procedure done in order to establish communication between two formerly distant portions of the bowel. This surgical procedure restores bowel continuity after the removal of a pathological condition affecting the intestines. A dangerous complication of bowel anastomosis is anastomotic leak causing peritonitis, which is related with a high morbidity and mortality. Aims of this study was to recognize the risk factors for anastomotic leak and study the rate of early complications and mortality of intestinal anastomosis.

Methods: This prospective hospital based study was conducted at Department of General Surgery, SKMCH, Muzaffarpur, and Bihar from March 2024 to August 2024. A total of 50 patients undergoing resection and anastomosis for different diseases were studied. Information was collected from detailed history, clinical examination and investigations (both hematological and radiological investigations) on the patients.

Results: In present study, there were 30 male patients (60%) and 20(40%) female patients. The age of the patients in this study ranged from 18 to 85 years. 43(86%) patients underwent anastomosis in the emergency setting and 7(14%) underwent anastomosis in elective setting. In this study out of 50 total patients, 46 patients (92%) underwent end to end anastomosis, 2 patients (4%) underwent end to side anastomosis and 2 patients (4%) underwent side to side anastomosis. The risk factors which are known to influence the outcome of bowel anastomosis particularly the occurrence of the anastomotic leak were observed and recorded including age, anaemia, hypoalbuminaemia, emergency surgery, peri-operative use of steroids, and intra-abdominal sepsis.

Conclusion: Intestinal anastomosis carries with it considerable mortality and the morbidity. Emergency small bowel anastomoses and intra-abdominal infection have a great risk of anastomotic leak despite attention to technical details during the procedure. Anastomotic leak rate is unaffected by the type of anastomosis performed.

Keywords: Bowel, Prognostic, Anastomosis, Leak, Mortality.

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Introduction

An anastomosis is approximation of two hollow viscera. It is a routinely performed procedure in a surgical emergency. Intestinal anastomosis dates back to 1000 B.C. Sushruta has described the use of red ants for intestinal anastomosis. [1] Different techniques have evolved during the last few decades. Laparoscopic stapled anastomosis is the preferred technique now in many advanced centers. In the 19th century, Travers and Lambert first performed double layer intestinal anastomosis.[2,3] In 1976 single layer interrupted anastomosis was described by Hautefeuille.[5] Anastomosis may be

everted, inverted, side to side, end to side, end to end, single layer, double layer, interrupted or continuous. The sutures used may be absorbable, non-absorbable, mono filament or braided. Hand sewn anastomosis is a commonly preferred technique as it is easy to perform with available suture materials. Early complications like anastomotic leak, peritonitis, faecal or biliary fistula, abscess, necrosis, stricture and late complications like intestinal obstruction increases the morbidity and mortality in patients. The

frequency of anastomotic leakage ranges from 1-24%. [4,6]

Material and Methods

This prospective hospital based study was conducted at Department of General Surgery, SKMCH, Muzaffarpur, and Bihar from March 2024 to August 2024. Data was collected from detailed history, clinical examination and investigations (both hematological as well as radiological) on the patients. A total of 50 patients undergoing resection and anastomosis for various diseases and indications were studied.

All the patients (aged above 18yrs) admitted to surgical wards and undergoing intestinal resection and primary anastomosis during study period at SKMCH, Muzaffarpur, and Bihar. Patients aged below 18yrs. Patients undergoing an initial diversion procedure and simple closure of stoma later. Patients undergoing gastrointestinal and biliary-enteric anastomosis. Patients aged below 18yrs, initial diversion procedure and simple closure of stoma later and gastrointestinal and biliary-enteric anastomosis were excluded in this study.

Methods

The relevant data required for the study were collected by using:

1. Detailed history
2. Hematological investigations: Hemoglobin, Serum Proteins and Albumin, Serum Electrolytes-Sodium and Potassium.
3. Radiological investigations like X-Rays and CT Scans when required.
4. Operative Details and Techniques Used.
5. Post-operative follow up for any early complications till the discharge of patient.

Comparisons between groups were analyzed by the chi-square test and p value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

The total number of cases observed and studied was 50. The study included the patients undergoing both emergency and elective surgeries with various indications for resection and anastomosis of bowel during the study period. These patients were considered for the study using the inclusion and exclusion criteria as mentioned above.

In present study, there were 30(60%) male patients and 20(40%) female patients. The age of the patients in this study ranged from 18 to 84 years. (Table 1)

Table 1: Demographic distribution of study population

Age group (in years)	Gender		Total No. of Patients	Percentage
	Male	Female		
<20	2	2	4	4%
20-39	11	5	16	32%
40-59	8	4	12	24%
>30	9	9	18	36%
Total	30	20	50	100%

In the table 2, out of 50 total patients, 46 patients (92%) underwent end to end anastomosis, 2 patients (2%) underwent end to side anastomosis and 2 patients (4%) underwent side to side anastomosis.

Table 2: Distribution of type of anastomosis in the study population

Type	No. of cases	Percentage
End to end Anastomosis (EEA)	46	92%
End to side anastomosis (ESA)	2	4%
Side to side Anastomosis (SSA)	2	4%
Total	50	100%

Table no. 3 shows, number of patients aged 60 years and above in this study is 18(36%). The rate of anastomotic leak is 27.77% (5 patients) and p value is 0.459(<.05).

Table 3: Incidence of anastomotic leak in old age group

Age 60 & above	Anastomotic Leak		Total	Percentage
	No.	Yes		
Yes	13	05	18	36%
No	26	6	32	64%
Total	39	11	50	100%

As shown in table 4, a total of 15 patients (30%) had anaemia in this study. The anastomotic leak rate in anaemic patients is 40% (6 patients) and p value is 0.044 (<0.05).

Table 4: Incidence of anastomotic leak in anaemic patients

	No Leak	Leak	Total No. of patients	Percentage
Yes	9	6	15	30%
No	30	5	35	70%
Total	39	11	50	100%

Postoperative morbidity was observed in 15(30%) patients. Most frequently observed complication was the Surgical Site Infection (26%). The observed complications were as in table no. 5.

Table 5: Complications observed and number of patients affected

Complications	No. of patients	Percentage
Surgical Site Infection	13	26%
Anastomotic disruption	11	22%
Septicaemia	7	14%
Acute Renal Failure	3	6%
Respiratory complications	5	10%
Abdominal wound dehiscence (Burst abdomen)	2	4%

Discussion

A dangerous complication of intestinal anastomosis is anastomotic leak causing peritonitis, which results in high morbidity and mortality rates. The factors which add to anastomotic leak include hypoalbuminemia¹⁶, advanced age, presence of intraabdominal sepsis^[7], rectal location of the disease, ASA grade 2 or above^[8], perioperative blood transfusion^[9] and anaemia^[11,12]. The rate of anastomotic leak observed in this thesis is 22%. The reported rate of anastomotic leak ranges between 0.8 to 35%. Hypoalbuminemia, intra-abdominal sepsis, anemia, old age and perioperative steroid use were the prognostic factors which were found to be statistically significant.

Hypoalbuminemia is very crucial for development of anastomotic leak. Most common procedure in our study was emergent small bowel resection and anastomosis (60%). Amit et al [10] reported a mortality rate of 17.1% in their prospective study on patients undergoing emergent small bowel resection. H Westapel et al [13] reported that the mortality rate of 18% and it increased to 30% in patients with no history of previous abdominal surgeries. Only 4 of our patients gave history of previous abdominal operations. 2 patients developed abdominal wound dehiscence in this study and all of them had low serum albumin levels.

In all, 8 of 50 patients were re-operated (16%). The indications for surgery in 2 of them was anastomotic dehiscence and 6 were operated for drainage of intra-abdominal abscess. The strong point of this thesis is its prospective nature.

Conclusion

Intestinal anastomosis carries with it considerable mortality and the morbidity. Emergency small bowel anastomoses and intra-abdominal infection have a great risk of anastomotic leak despite attention to technical details during the procedure.

Anastomotic leak rate is unaffected by the type of anastomosis performed. Malnourished (those with low serum albumin levels) patients are at a greater risk for developing anastomotic leak, SSI, morbidity & mortality following bowel anastomosis. Serum albumin levels can be used as a simple, reliable and economical prognostic marker in predicting the outcome of bowel anastomoses. This helps the surgeon in operative decision making as well as explaining the prognosis and operative risk to the patient. Patients with intra-abdominal sepsis and patients treated with perioperative corticosteroids for pulmonary disease carry a significant risk for anastomotic dehiscence.

Therefore in this patient category, it is recommended that anastomoses should be protected by a diverting stoma. In the emergency setting, malnourished patients (after attending the primary pathology) should be ideally considered for creation of a temporary stoma to tide the crisis over and closure of stoma considered in second setting. However if an anastomosis is deemed necessary, these patients should be observed thoroughly for any signs of leak postoperatively and should be intervened at the earliest. Considering enteral nutritional optimization before elective surgery may be useful in reducing the morbidity and mortality rate.

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